

Strengthening Organizational Climate, Transformational Leadership and Adversity to Improve Teacher Performance: An Empirical Study on Private Junior High School Teachers in Depok City

Ibnu Hasan, Thamrin Abdullah, Widodo Sunaryo

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teachers, Education, transformational leadership, Teacher Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5093920</p>	<p><i>Education is a decisive sector to print the whole human being, namely humans who have balance and intellectual, emotional and spiritual intelligence in living life. When a person wants to achieve this balance then he must get the intake of physical needs, knowledge and spiritual needs. If the three needs are met, a person will have strong adversity in dealing with various dynamics of life, challenges, and high resilience in the face of obstacles and difficulties that exist in his life. In order to create a learning atmosphere and a supportive learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state, the role of a teacher is important part in improving the quality of education. As educators, teachers are educational leaders who are very decisive in the learning process in the classroom. This leadership role will be reflected in how teachers carry out their duties. This means that teacher performance is a very decisive factor for the quality of education.</i></p>

Introduction

Good teacher performance must be supported by an organizational climate, transformational leadership of school principals and resilience against adversity. The Government of the Republic of Indonesia has set development targets in the field of national education to improve the quality of education in the 2004-2009 National Long-Term Development Program which is marked with; (1) the availability of national education sources and minimum service standards for the City/Regency level, (2) increasing the proportion of educators in the formal and non-formal education pathways who have teaching qualifications, (3) increasing the proportion of both public and private education units that are accredited either , (4) increase the percentage of students who pass the final exam at each level of education, (5) increase interest in reading Indonesian people (Regulation of the Government of the Republic of Indonesia Number 7 of 2005). Given the importance of the role of teacher performance on the quality of education and human resources in Indonesia, it is very reasonable to assume that the reality of the achievement of the Human Development Index in Indonesia has not been in line with expectations, one of which is the result of not optimal teacher performance. This can be seen in the report of The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) for the last two years (2015-2016) on the Development Index in the medium category of 188 participants surveyed (UNDP, 2016). The not yet optimal performance of teachers can be seen from the acquisition of the results of the national junior high school teacher competency test, where the average value reaches 65.33 out of a scale of 100 (Balitbang, 2016). The results of the teacher's competence are a reflection of the not yet optimal improvement in teacher performance, which of course is related to the achievement of educational goals. While the teacher's performance is not optimal, it is certainly related to many variables.

The government through the Ministry of Education and Culture has started an educational revolution since 2019, both at the elementary, middle and high levels. The concept promoted in this revolution is freedom to learn in all aspects of formal education. The concept of Freedom of Learning and Education 4.0 The concept of independent learning is very different from the existing curriculum and is used by formal education in Indonesia. This new educational concept takes into account the individual cognitive abilities and uniqueness of the students. The following outlines some of them: Minimum competency assessment. The difference between this new educational concept and the previously used curriculum is that students are expected to be able to demonstrate minimum skills in terms of "literacy" and "numerics." The focus is not how much students are able to get grades through assignments from the teacher, but how students are able to think critically using their cognitive abilities. Next Character survey In the concept of a character survey, the government will thoroughly assess the quality of education in schools. It is not only about learning outcomes, but also the available educational ecosystem and infrastructure. In other words, the development of the quality of education is no longer about implementing fixed quality indicators, but based on data from the latest survey of schools. Next is

the expansion of the assessment of learning outcomes, one of the most interesting things in the concept of "free learning" is the expansion of student learning outcomes assessment which was previously only based on national exam scores, into assignments and portfolios.

Next is the equal distribution of education quality up to the 3T, namely Freedom of Learning can also be interpreted as justice for equal access to education for all students in Indonesia. Therefore, the government made an affirmation policy and provided a special quota for students living in the 3T area.

Based on the results of the author's preliminary study to 30 teachers at five junior high schools in Depok City, it shows that there are teacher performance problems, namely the teacher's performance has not been achieved in accordance with the target. The complete preliminary survey results are as follows There are 38% of teachers who have problems with the quantity of work, which can be seen from the number of teachers who have problems in optimizing learning facilities and are not able to complete the work carefully, carefully and carefully. There are 39% of teachers who have problems with work efficiency, which can be seen from the number of teachers who have problems with being present at the morning ceremony at the office and the inability of teachers to use their skills to produce good work.. There are 40% of teachers who have problems with work performance, which can be seen from the number of teachers who have problems understanding their work and duties, and teachers do not have the ability to solve existing problems related to their work.. There are 43% of teachers who have problems in the quality of work, which can be seen from the number of teachers who have problems in doing their work so that they do not carry out their work optimally and teachers are not able to complete work targets properly. There are 30% of teachers who have problems in cooperation, which can be seen from the number of teachers who have problems in terms of increasing self-efficacy through training, guidance and direction as well as the inability of teachers to optimize excellence in themselves at work. The success of a school organization will not be separated from the quality of teacher performance in carrying out their duties as a profession. In its operationalization, teacher performance can be implemented by applying various basic competencies possessed by teachers in an effort to improve the quality of education so that the quality of teacher performance can be realized as expected.

Based on the background described above, teacher performance is determined by many factors including transformational leadership, job satisfaction, organizational climate, organizational commitment, organizational culture, work behavior, decision making, work discipline, interpersonal communication, and adversity. The low transformational leadership of superiors so that it has an impact on the low stimulation and inspiration of teachers as subordinates in achieving high work results so that it is suspected to be related to teacher performance. Organizational climate, in this case a comfortable, safe and orderly school will have an impact on the good and development of a good organizational climate in the school. If the organizational climate is low, it will have an impact on teacher performance in achieving organizational goals. Weak organizational commitment in this case the school has an impact on teacher performance, so it is necessary to motivate teachers by superiors so that teacher performance does not go in a bad or negative direction. Low work behavior makes teachers less able to provide examples and make positive contributions to schools. Low work behavior also makes teachers not make positive contributions to institutions, in this case schools. Weak decision-making will have an impact on schools so that teacher performance experiences obstacles. The decision-making process that is too convoluted will make the teacher's performance slow.. Poor Interpersonal Communication gives birth to mutual suspicion and excessive suspicion will make communication run not optimally so that teacher performance does not improve properly. The ability of teachers to withstand adversity or survive in situations that occur around them affects teacher performance in determining organizational progress or setbacks in schools.. Low organizational culture causes low behavioral norms and values that are understood and accepted by employees as members of the organization which are used as the basis for behavior in the organization so that it is suspected to be related to employee performance.. Dissatisfaction with the work of the teacher causes the teacher's motivation to be low in enjoying the work so that in the end there will not grow awareness from within the teacher to be able to complete his work as well as possible so that it is suspected to be related to teacher performance. Low teacher work discipline will cause teachers to not obey the rules, norms, laws and regulations that apply in the organization so that teachers tend not to implement and obey them, do not guarantee efforts to maintain order and the smooth implementation of work so that it is suspected to be related to teacher performance.

Based on the theoretical study and framework that has been described previously, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

1. There is a positive relationship between organizational climate and teacher performance, so strengthening Organizational Climate can improve teacher performance.
2. There is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance so that strengthening transformational leadership with teacher performance can improve teacher performance.

3. There is a positive relationship between disaster resilience and teacher performance so that the strengthening of the disaster resilience climate can improve teacher performance.
4. There is a positive relationship between organizational climate, transformational leadership and adversity together with teacher performance so that strengthening organizational climate, transformational leadership and adversity resilience with teacher performance can improve teacher performance.
5. There is a positive relationship between organizational climate and transformational leadership with teacher performance so that strengthening organizational climate and transformational leadership with teacher performance can improve teacher performance.
6. There is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and resilience with teacher performance so that strengthening transformational leadership and resilience to teacher performance can improve teacher performance.
7. There is a positive relationship between organizational climate, transformational leadership and adversity with teacher performance so that strengthening organizational climate, transformational leadership and resilience with teacher performance can improve teacher performance.

Fig. 1. Research Model

Information :

- X1 = Organizational Climate Independent Variable
- X2 = Transformational Leadership Independent Variable
- X3 = Accident Resilience Independent Variable
- Y = Teacher Performance Bound Variable
- = Epsilon (Other Variable)

METHOD

The research was carried out limited to Permanent Teachers of Private Junior High Schools accredited A in Depok, West Java Province. The research was carried out within a year, starting from the approval of the research proposal with details of research activities presented in the following table: The research method used was a causal survey method with correlation techniques. The empirical data to be collected consists of three independent variables, namely Organizational Climate (X1), Transformational Leadership (X2) and Disadvantages (X3) with the dependent variable being Teacher Performance (Y). compiled based on the indicators that exist in the research variables. The primary data needed are data on Organizational Climate, Transformational Leadership, Adversity Resilience and Teacher Performance. The research will begin with the instrument-making stage, then continue with the instrument-testing stage with statistical calculations. The next stage is instrument validation and instrument reliability, followed by the distribution of instruments to respondents. The research context describes the relationship between Organizational Climate, Transformational Leadership, Barriers to Teacher Performance.

Population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions are drawn. (Sugiyono, 2016:148). The population of this research is the permanent teachers of accredited private junior high schools in Depok City based on the School Data of the Ministry of Education and Culture obtained data of accredited private junior high schools A totaling 92 junior high schools with the number of permanent teachers foundation as many as 1152 people in 11 sub-districts consisting of 5 Regions, namely the Northern Region, Eastern Region, Central Region, Southern Region and Western Region.

The validity (validity) of the Teacher Performance instrument items is based on the Pearson Product Moment correlation test. According to Sugiyono (2017:228) Pearson's Product Moment technique is used to find a relationship and prove the hypothesis of a relationship between two variables if the variable data is in the form of an interval or ratio, and the data sources of the two or more variables are the same. The data is processed using the Pearson coefficient formula with $\alpha = 0.05$, then compare the calculated r value with the r table from a total score of 40 questions tested. If the result of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, the statement item is declared valid. Test the depth (reliability) of the Teacher Performance instrument by using the Cornbach Alpha correlation. According to Suharsimi Arikunto (2010: p.239), the Alpha formula is used to find the reliability of an instrument whose score is not 1 or 0, for example a questionnaire or a question form description. Reliability measures relate to the consistency and accuracy of measurements. The results are concluded that if $r_{count} > 0.7$ then the instrument is declared reliable and can be used as a data collection tool. The minimum construct reliability value is 0.70 as sufficient reliability.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study proposes seven hypotheses whose proof needs to be tested empirically. The seven hypotheses are tentative conjectures regarding the relationship between Organizational Climate (X1), Transformational Leadership (X2), and Adversity Resilience (X3) either individually or jointly with Teacher Performance (Y). Hypothesis testing is done by correlation and regression analysis. Testing the first, second and third hypotheses using simple correlation and regression analysis, while the fourth to seventh using multiple correlations, more recently each hypothesis will be tested with the following evidence:

Table 1: Summary of Research Hypothesis Testing Results

No	Corelation	Corelation coefficient	Sig correlation		Conclusion
			(Sig)	$\alpha=0,05$	
1.	X ₁ and Y	$r_{y1} = 0,926$	0,000	0,05	H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance
2.	X ₂ and Y	$r_{y2} = 0,937$	0,000	0,05	H1 is accepted. There is a relationship positive relationship between Transformational Leadership and Teacher Performance
3.	X ₃ and Y	$r_{y3} = 0,902$	0,000	0,05	H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Adversity

Resilience and Teacher Performance					
4.	X ₁ and X ₂ and Y	ry ₁₂ = 0,690	0,000	0,05	H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate and Transformational Leadership with Teacher Performance
5.	X ₁ and X ₃ and Y	ry ₁₃ = 0,742	0,000	0,05	H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate and Adversity Resilience with Teacher Performance
6.	X ₂ and X ₃ and Y	ry ₂₃ = 0,813	0,000	0,05	H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Transformational Leadership and Adversity Resilience with Teacher Performance
7.	X ₁ , X ₂ and X ₃ and Y	ry ₁₂₃ = 0,819	0,000	0,05	H1 is accepted. There is a positive relationship between Organizational Climate and Transformational Leadership and Adversity with Teacher Performance

Table 2. Partial Correlation Test Results between Adversity Resilience and Teacher Performance Transformational Leadership Control

Control Variables				Teacher Performance (Y)	Adversity (X ₃)	Performance (X ₂)
-none ^a	Teacher Performance (Y)	Correlation	(1-	1,000	0,902	0,937
		Significance tailed)			0,000	0,000
		df		0	184	184
	Adversity (X ₃)	Correlation	(1-	0,902	1,000	0,884
		Significance tailed)		0,000		0,000
		df		184	0	184
	Org Climate (X ₁)	Correlation	(1-	0,937	0,884	1,000
		Significance tailed)		0,000	0,000	
		df		184	184	0
Leadership Transformational (X ₂)	Performance (Y)	Correlation	(1-	1,000	0,450	
		Significance tailed)			0,000	
		df		0	183	
	Adversity (X ₃)	Correlation	(1-	0,450	1,000	
		Significance tailed)		0,000		
		df		183	0	

a. Cells contain zero-order (Pearson) correlations.

In table 2 the results of the partial correlation test between adversity resistance (X3) and Teacher Performance (Y) with the transformational leadership control variable (X2) obtained a partial correlation coefficient (r_{y31}) of 0.450. The correlation coefficient is quite significant ($\text{sig. } 0.000 < 0.05$). It can be concluded that partially adversity resistance (X3) has a positive and significant relationship with teacher performance (Y). This means that the relationship between adversity resistance (X3) and teacher performance (Y) is not influenced by transformational leadership (X2).

Table 3: Summary of Partial Correlation Significance Test

No	Correlation	Control	Coefficient Correlation	Significant Test		Conclusion
				Sig	α	
1	Y-X ₁	X ₂	$r_{y12} = 0.231$	0.002	0.05	Sig
2	Y-X ₁	X ₃	$r_{y13} = 0.598$	0.000	0.05	Sig
3	Y-X ₂	X ₁	$r_{y21} = 0,438$	0.000	0.05	Sig
4	Y-X ₂	X ₃	$r_{y23} = 0.693$	0.000	0.05	Sig
5	Y-X ₃	X ₁	$r_{y13} = 0.399$	0.000	0.05	Sig
6	Y-X ₃	X ₂	$r_{y23} = 0,813$	0.000	0.05	Sig

1. The Relationship between Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance

The results showed that there was a significant relationship between Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance. Based on the results of research with hypothesis testing, it is known that the correlation coefficient between Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance (r_{y1}) is 0.926 with the category having a very strong relationship. The probability value is $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 is rejected, so it can be concluded that the correlation coefficient is significant. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant relationship between Organizational Climate and Teacher Performance. The diversity in teacher performance related to organizational climate is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.844 or 84.4%, while the remaining 15.6% is influenced by other factors.

The results of this study get the equation $Y = -114,618 + 1,764.X_1$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on organizational climate scores, it can be predicted that every 1 increase in organizational climate score will increase teacher performance by 1,764 times at a constant -114,618.

2. The Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Teacher Performance

The results of the study which show that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance are interpreted that lecturers who have high transformational leadership will have an impact on high teacher performance. The strength of the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance is reflected in the correlation coefficient value of 0.937 with a very strong relationship level category. The probability value ($\text{sig } 0.000 < 0.05$), it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected, it can be interpreted that there is a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance. The diversity in teacher performance related to transformational leadership is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.873 or 87.3%, while the remaining 12.7% is influenced by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $Y = -41.896 + 1.303.X_2$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on transformational leadership scores, it can be predicted that every 1 increase in transformational leadership scores will increase teacher performance by 1.303 times at a constant -41.896.

3. The Relationship between Resilience and Teacher Performance

The results of the study which showed that there was a significant relationship between adversity resistance and teacher performance meant that teachers who had high adversity resistance would have an impact on high teacher performance. The strength of the relationship between adversity and teacher performance is reflected in the correlation coefficient value of 0.902 with a very strong relationship level category. The probability value ($\text{sig } 0.00 < 0.05$), it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected, it can be interpreted that there is a significant positive relationship between adversity resistance and teacher performance. The diversity in teacher performance related to resilience is reflected in the coefficient of determination of 0.915 or 91.5%, while the remaining 8.5% is influenced by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $Y = -94.526 + 1.606.X_3$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on the score of resilience. This means that the equation can be predicted that every 1 increase in the score of misfortune will increase teacher performance by 1,606 times at a constant -94,526

4. Relationship between Organizational Climate and Transformational Leadership and Teacher Performance. The results of the study show that there is a positive relationship between organizational climate and transformational leadership together with teacher performance. It means that if the teacher shows a good organizational climate and has good transformational leadership, the teacher's performance will be good. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between organizational climate and transformational leadership with teacher performance (r_{y12}) of 0.690 means that it has a very strong relationship level category, with a probability value (sig) of $0.000 < 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a relationship between organizational climate and transformational leadership with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and transformational leadership with teacher performance. The diversity in teacher performance which can be explained due to the influence of organizational climate and transformational leadership is obtained from the value of the coefficient of determination of 0.476 which means that 47.6% of teacher performance factors are determined jointly by organizational climate and transformational leadership with teacher performance while 52.4% the rest is determined by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $Y = 32.332 - 0.532X_1 + 1.311X_2$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on organizational climate scores and transformational leadership. This means that the equation can predict that every 1 increase in organizational climate and transformational leadership scores will simultaneously increase teacher performance by 1.311 times for transformational leadership variables and -0.532 times for organizational climate variables at a constant 32,332.

5. Relationship between Organizational Climate and Adversity Resilience and Teacher Performance
The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and adversity with teacher performance. Based on the results of the study, it was obtained that the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between organizational climate and adversity with teacher performance was obtained. (r_{y13}) of 0.742 with a strong relationship category, with a probability value (sig) of $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a significant relationship between organizational climate and adversity with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational climate and resilience together with teacher performance. Contribution of organizational climate and resilience to teacher performance. (r^2_{y13}) of 0.551 which can be interpreted that 55.1% of teacher performance factors are determined jointly by organizational climate and resilience. while the remaining 44.9% is determined by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $= 24,445 - 1,570X_1 + 2,327X_3$ which can be used to predict teacher performance based on organizational climate scores and adversity resistance. This means that the equation can predict that every 1 increase in organizational climate and adversity scores will simultaneously increase teacher performance by 2.327 times for the variable resilience to adversity and -1.570 times for the organizational climate variable at a constant 24,445.

6. Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Adversity with Teacher Performance.
The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and adversity with teacher performance. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between transformational leadership and adversity with teacher performance (r_{y23}) was 0.813 with a very strong category, with a probability value (sig) of $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 was rejected meaning that there was a significant relationship between transformational leadership and adversity with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and adversity together with teacher performance. The contribution of transformational leadership and resilience to teacher performance (r^2_{y23}) is 0.661, which means that 66.1% of teacher performance factors are determined jointly by transformational leadership and adversity while the remaining 33.9% is determined by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $= -95.253 - 2.280X_2 + 3.773X_3$ which can be used to predict teacher performance based on transformational leadership scores and adversity resilience. This means that the equation can predict that each increase in the score of transformational leadership and resilience together will increase teacher performance by 3.773 times for the variable resilience and -2.280 times for the variable transformational leadership at a constant -95.253.

7. Relationship between Organizational Climate, Transformational Leadership and Adversity with Teacher Performance dengan

The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between organizational climate, transformational leadership and adversity with teacher performance. Based on the results of the study, the correlation coefficient value of the relationship between organizational climate, transformational leadership and adversity with teacher performance (r_{y123}) was 0.819 with a very strong category, with a probability value (sig) $0.000 < 0.005$, then H_0 was rejected, meaning that there was a significant relationship between organizational climate, transformational leadership and resilience with teacher performance. Thus, this study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational climate, transformational leadership and resilience together with teacher performance. The contribution of organizational climate, transformational leadership and resilience to teacher performance (r^2_{y123}) is 0.671 which can be interpreted that 67.1% of diversity in teacher performance can be explained by organizational climate, transformational leadership and adversity while the remaining 32.9% is determined by other factors. The results of this study get the equation $= -125.780 + 0.780X_1 - 2.712X_2 + 3.626X_3$ can be used to predict teacher performance based on organizational climate scores, transformational leadership and adversity resilience. This means that the equation can predict that every 1 increase in organizational climate score, transformational leadership and adversity will simultaneously increase teacher performance by 3.626 times for the resilience variable, -2.712 times for the transformational leadership variable and 0.780 times for the organizational climate variable at a constant -125,780.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research at the quantitative stage and the qualitative research stage, it can be concluded that this study has found efforts to improve the performance of private A-accredited Junior High School (SMP) teachers in Depok City, West Java Province through organizational climate, transformational leadership, and resilience to adversity, based on identification as follows. There is a significant positive relationship with the strength of the very strong category relationship between organizational climate variables and teacher performance, so strengthening organizational climate can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship with the strength of a very strong categorical relationship between the variables of transformational leadership and teacher performance, so that strengthening transformational leadership can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship with the strength of a strong categorical relationship between organizational climate variables and transformational leadership variables together with teacher performance, so that strengthening organizational climate and transformational leadership together with teacher performance can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship with the strength of the strong categorical relationship between organizational climate variables and resilience variables together with performance, so that strengthening organizational climate and resilience together with teacher performance can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship with the strength of the very strong categorical relationship between the transformational leadership variable and the variable of adversity resistance together with teacher performance, so that strengthening transformational leadership and resilience together with teacher performance can improve teacher performance. There is a significant positive relationship with the strength of a strong categorical relationship between organizational climate variables, transformational leadership variables and adversity variables together with teacher performance, so that strengthening organizational climate and transformational leadership and resilience together with teacher performance can improve teacher performance.

This research was conducted with the aim of finding efforts to improve teacher performance through the development of an organizational climate, transformational leadership and disaster resilience in A-accredited Private Junior High Schools (SMP) in Depok City, West Java Province. meet the criteria or indicators of teacher performance.

Teacher performance indicators are 1). Quantity: Principals need to direct their attention to efforts to increase teacher commitment; 2). Quality: Principals need to guide how to improve teacher quality; 3). Acceleration of Work: To improve the quality of each job, it is necessary to accelerate the work of the teacher; 4). Effectiveness In the activities of teachers, more and more plans have been achieved; 5). Efficient: in a learning process at school use resources sparingly to achieve optimal. Based on this research, teacher performance can be developed through an organizational climate, transformational leadership and adversity resilience either individually or together. In fact, the three independent variables make a positive contribution to the increase in the dependent variable of teacher performance. Therefore, the implications for improving teacher performance are needed as follows: 1. There is a relationship between organizational climate and teacher performance, indicating that with increasing organizational climate, teacher performance will also increase. Several efforts must be made, namely by improving the organizational climate on indicators of the physical environment, social environment and management system so as to improve teacher performance later. There is a relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance, indicating that with increasing transformational leadership, teacher performance also increases. Several efforts must be made, namely by increasing transformational leadership on indicators of the influence of idealism, motivational inspiration, intellectual driving and management systems so that they can improve teacher performance later.

Several efforts must be made, namely by improving the organizational climate in the physical environment, social environment and management system as well as transformational leadership on indicators of the influence of idealism, motivational inspiration, intellectual encouragement and special attention so as to improve teacher performance later. together with teacher performance, shows that with increasing organizational climate and disaster resilience together with teacher performance. Several efforts must be made, namely by improving the organizational climate in the physical environment, social environment and management system as well as adversity resistance on control indicators, original ownership, reach and endurance so as to improve teacher performance later. There is a relationship between transformational leadership and adversity resilience together with teacher performance, indicating that with increased transformational leadership and resilience together with teacher performance. Several efforts must be made, namely by increasing transformational leadership on indicators of the influence of idealism, inspiration and motivation, intellectual encouragement and special attention and resilience to adversity on indicators of control, original ownership, reach and endurance so that it can improve teacher performance later. The relationship between organizational climate, transformational leadership and disaster resilience together with teacher performance, shows that with increasing organizational climate, transformational leadership and disaster resilience together with teacher performance increases. Several efforts must be made, namely by improving the organizational climate on indicators of the physical environment, social environment and management system, and transformational leadership on transformational leadership on indicators of idealism influence, motivating inspiration, intellectual driving and special attention and resilience to adversity on indicators of control, original ownership, reach. (achieve) and endurance (endurance) so that it can improve teacher performance later. The results of this study produce findings that must be improved so that teacher performance increases to the maximum with indicators that are already well recommended to be maintained such as indicators on organizational climate variables (physical environment, social environment and management system), on transformational leadership variables (idealism influence), motivational inspiration, intellectual encouragement and special attention), on the variables of control, ownership, reach and endurance and on the teacher performance variables (effectiveness and efficiency). The results of this study produce findings that must be improved. so that teacher performance increases maximally with indicators that are not yet good for improvement such as quantity, quality and acceleration of work, all of this is on the teacher's performance variable.

REFERENCES

- A.A Anwar Prabu Mangkunegaran. 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Angelo Kinicki dan Brian K. Williams. *Managemen A Practical Introduction*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2008. pp. 489 – 491
- Anthonia Adenike. 2011. “Organizational Climate as A Predictor of Employee Job Satisfaction: Evidence from Covenant University”. *Business Intelligence Journal*, Volume. 14, No. 1, , pp. 151-165.
- Awolusi Olawumi Dele, 2015, Ayoade Omisade Ezekiel, Lawal Fatai Alani. Koys and De Cottis. *Strategic Human Resource Management and Organizational Climate in the Nigerian Banking Industry*. (American Journal of Environmental Policy and Management

- Bass, B. M. And Avolio, B. J. *Improving Organizational Effectiveness Through Transformasional Leadership*. Sage Thousand Oaks. 2004. Pp. 263-273
- Bernard M. Bass dan Ronald E. Riggio. *Transformational Leadership*. London: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers, 2006, pp. 6
- Davis dan JW Newstrom. *Human Behaviour at Work: Organizational Behaviour*. Singapore.: Mc. Graw-Hill Company, 2003. pp, 40-41.
- Debra L. Nelson and James Campbell Quick, *Organizational Behavior, Foundations, Realities, & Challenges 5th edition*, (America: Thomson South Western: 2006), pp.191-193
- Encep Safrudin Muhyi, 2011. *Kepemimpinan Pendidikan Transformasional*, Jakarta: Diadit Media Press.
- F.C Lunenburg & A.C. Ornstein. *Educational Administration Concepts and Practoce, Third Edition*. (Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Thomson Learning, 2005). p. 74
- Fendy Suhariadi. 2005. "Deskripsi Adversity Quotient dan Perilaku Produktif dari Pemogok Kerja". *Jurnal INSAN Media Psikologi*, Volume. 7, No 1, pp. 49-50.
- Fred Walumbwa, Bruce Avolio dan Weichun Zhu. 2008. "How Transformational Leadership Weaves Its Influence on Individual Job Performance: The Role of Identification and Efficacy Beliefs". *Personnel Psychology* 61:4, pp. 793 – 825
- Gary Yuki. 2010. *Kepemimpinan Dalam Organisasi*. Edisi Kelima. Jakarta: PT Indeks
- Imanol Belausteguigoitia, Juana Patlán, and María Mercedes Navarrete J. 2007. "Organizational Climate as Antecedent of Commitment, Effort and Entrepreneurial Orientation in Mexican Family and Non-Family firms". *Revista del Centro de Investigacion, Universidad La Salle (Méx.)*, Volume. 7. Núm. 27. Ene, pp. 5-24.
- J.A. Colquitt, J. LePine, and M. Wesson. *Organizational Behavior*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2009. pp. 477
- Jason A. Colquitt, Jeffery A. Lepine, and Michael J. Wesson, *Organizational Behavior Improving Performance and Commitment in the Workplace*, (New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin: 2009) pp.38-42, 52-57
- Jean Marie Candoa dan Luni Villacastinb. 2014. "Influence of Motivation and Culture on Organizational, Commitment and Performance on Employee of Medical Services". *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, Volume 18, No 2, pp. 354-367 Volume 1, Issue 3, November, pp. 227-234.
- Kaushik Kundu. 2007. "Development of the Conceptual Framework of Organizational Climate". *Vidyasagar University Journal of Commerce*, Volume. 12, pp. 99-108.
- Khrisnan, Verkat R. Impact of Transformasional Leadership on Followers' Influence Strategies, *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*. 2004. Vol. 25, pp. 35
- Luthans, F. *Organizations Behavior*. New York: McGraw Hill International. 2002, pp. 430 – 431
- Malcolm G. Patterson, Michael A. West, Viv J. Shackleton, Jeremy F. Dawson, Rebecca Lawthom, Sally Maitlis, David L. Robinson, and Alison M. Wallace. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, No. 26, 2005
- Maria C.J. Santos. 2012. "Assessing the Effectiveness of the Adapted Adversity Quotient Program in Special Education School". *International Refereed Journal*, Volume. 3, Issue 4(2), pp. 13-23
- Mary Uhl-Bien, John R. Schermerhorn, Jr., & Richard N. Osborn. *Organizational Behavior*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2014, p. 13
- Nurharani Selamat Nur Zahira, Samsu Nur Shaminah dan Mustafa Kamalu. 2013. "The Impact Of Organizational Climate on Teachers' Job Performance" *Educational Research*, Volume 2, No. 1, pp. 71-82.
- Rachapoom Pangma, Sombat Tayraukham, and Prasar Nuangchalerm. 2009. *Journal of Social Science*, Volume. 5, No. 4, pp. 466-470
- Richard L. Daft, *New Era Of Management Ninth Edition*. (Canada: South-Western Cengage Learning: 2010), pp. 8, 23, 382
- Robert Stringer *Leadership and Organizational Climate*. New Jersey: Upper Saddler River, 2002, p. 45, 122
- Salleh Fauziah, Zaharah Dzulkifli, Wan Amalia Wan Abdullah dan Nur Haizal Maryakop, 2011. "The Effect of Motivation on Job Perfomance of State Government Employee's in Malaysia" *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. Volume 1, No. 4, pp.147-154.
- Sedarmayanti. 2009. *Sumber Daya Manusia dan Produktivitas Kerja*. Bandung: CV Mandar Maju.
- Slocum, John W dan Hellriegel, Don. *Organizational Behavior 13th Ed*. Mason: South Western, 2011, pp. 329-330
- Stephen P. Robbins and Mary Coulter, *Management 11th edition*. (New Jersey: 2012: Pearson), pp. 492
- Stoltz, Paul. 2007, *Adversity Quotient: Mengubah Hambatan Menjadi Peluang*. Alih Bahasa: Hermaya. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- Tabrani Rusyan dkk. 2000. *Upaya Meningkatkan Budaya Kinerja Guru*. Cianjur: CV Dinamika Karya Cipta.
- Topic Offirston, *Mutu Pendidikan Madrasah Tsanawiyah*, (Yogyakarta: Deepublish, 2014)
- Tony Wijaya. 2007. "Hubungan Adversity Intelligence dengan Intensi Berwirausaha". *Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan*, Volume. 9, No 2, pp. 117-12

Wirawan. 2008. *Budaya dan Iklim Organisasi*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.

Wutun, R.P. 2001. *Persepsi Karyawan tentang Perilaku Kepemimpinan Atasan*. Jakarta: Bagian Psikologi Industri dan Organisasi Fakultas Psikologi Universitas Indonesia.

Author Information

Ibnu Hasan

Pakuan University, Indonesia

Thamrin Abdullah

Pakuan University, Indonesia

Widodo Sunaryo

Pakuan University, Indonesia
